

**STUDY OF THE PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF BASALT FIBER
CONCRETE**

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Abstract. In this research work, the physical, mechanical, and operational properties of fine-grained basalt fiber concrete were studied. During the study, the influence of basalt fibers on the concrete composition was analyzed, specifically regarding strength, water resistance, and frost resistance indicators. According to the test results, it was found that basalt fibers are evenly distributed in the concrete matrix, reducing the formation of micro-cracks, increasing the density of the concrete, and forming closed pores. It was noted that the samples with the optimized composition withstand a water pressure of 1.6 MPa and comply with the W16 waterproofing grade. It was also established that basalt fibers increase the frost resistance of concrete and reduce internal stresses arising during freeze-thaw cycles. The research results show that basalt fiber concrete is a promising material for hydraulic structures, transport construction, and structures operating in aggressive environments.

Fine-grained basalt fiber concrete is distinguished by possessing essential operational properties such as high strength, frost resistance, and water resistance. The main reason for this is the uniform distribution of basalt fibers across the concrete matrix. The fibers perform the function of micro-reinforcement within the cement stone, reducing the accumulation of internal stresses at a single point and preventing the formation of micro-cracks. As a result, the compressive and bending strength of the concrete increases.

Furthermore, the use of basalt fibers contributes to an increase in the number of closed pores within the concrete composition. These closed pores reduce the internal pressure generated during freezing and thawing processes in cold climates. Consequently, the frost resistance of the concrete increases significantly, ensuring its long-term service without deformation. Furthermore, the dense structure of the concrete limits water penetration through capillary pathways, which improves the waterproofing properties of the material.

Basalt fiber concrete is also characterized by high wear resistance. The fibers increase the resistance of the concrete surface to abrasive effects, allowing for their effective use in road surfaces, industrial floors, and hydraulic structures. Furthermore, basalt fiber possesses high resistance to chemically active environments and corrosion, protecting concrete structures from the effects of aggressive environments. Thanks to these aspects, basalt fiber concrete is resistant to mechanical loads, climate change, and chemical influences, significantly extending the service life of structures.

Water resistance was assessed according to GOST 12730.5-2018, "Wet spot." Sample size $\varnothing=15$ cm, $h=15$ cm.

Table 1

Results of determining the water resistance of a control composition with a hydrophobic and optimized composition

Co	Water/Ce	Water pressure, MPa	
1	0,41	0,4	W-4
		0,6	W-6
		0,6	W-6
2	0,38	1,6	W-16
		1,6	W-16
		1,4	W-14

Figure 1. Scenes from the experimental work

To determine the waterproofing properties, the samples were tested under a gradually increasing water pressure. Initially, the water pressure was set at 0.2 MPa, and it was gradually increased in subsequent stages. Samples were held at each pressure level for 6 hours, and the water resistance of the concrete composition was observed. This method allows for the determination of concrete density and the degree of water permeability through capillary pores.

According to the test results, the optimized concrete composition successfully withstood water pressure up to 1.6 MPa, and no cases of water filtration or leakage on the surface of the samples were recorded during the test. This indicates that the concrete composition possesses a highly dense structure, while basalt fibers and fine-grained components strengthen the matrix and reduce capillary gaps.

After the test was completed, the samples were divided into two parts and the depth of water penetration into the concrete was measured. The results obtained confirmed that the internal layers of the concrete are practically impermeable to water. Based on the data presented in Table 1, it was established that the experimental composition corresponds to the W16 waterproofing grade. This indicator indicates that the concrete possesses high waterproofing properties, allowing it to be used in hydraulic structures, underground structures, water reservoirs, and facilities with high moisture exposure.

Study of the frost resistance of basalt-fiber concrete

According to the research results, it was determined that the frost resistance of fiberglass concrete is directly dependent on the fiber content. Specifically, when the glass fiber content was 0.5% and 1.5%, the concrete corresponded to the F400 frost resistance grade, while when the fiber content reached 3.5%, this indicator decreased to the F300 grade. The authors explain this situation by the fact that as a result of an increase in the amount of fibers, the convenience of placement and the compactability of the fibrous concrete mixture decrease. Insufficient

compaction of the mortar leads to the formation of additional pores in the cement stone. As a result, the probability of water accumulation inside the concrete increases, and the internal pressure generated during "freeze-melt" cycles reduces the frost resistance of the concrete. At the same time, studies have shown that the reinforcing fibers themselves in the composition of fibrous concrete do not wear out under the influence of cold and retain their strength.

The mechanism for increasing the frost resistance of basalt-fiber concrete is explained by a number of factors. First of all, the introduction of basalt fibers into the concrete mix increases the amount of air in the composition and contributes to the formation of small closed pores. These pores act as compensatory cavities for the volumetric expansion of frozen water during the "freeze-melt" process. As a result, the internal pressure generated inside the concrete decreases, and the risk of material corrosion decreases.

However, the main factor ensuring the high frost resistance of basalt-fiber concrete is the reinforcing effect of the fibers on the concrete matrix. Basalt fibers are firmly bonded to the cement stone, absorbing the tensile stresses generated within the concrete during the freezing process and limiting the development of micro-cracks. Thus, the integrity of the concrete composition is preserved, and the long-term operational reliability of the material is increased. It is precisely these properties that allow for the effective use of basalt-fiber concrete in conditions of a sharply continental climate in regions with repeated freeze-thaw cycles (Table 3.14).

Operational characteristics of fine-grained modified concrete

	Expenditure		compr essive strength, MPa	Ben ding strength limit, MPa	To axial compres sion (kg f/ cm ²)	F rost resist ance	Wat er permeab ility	Con crete class
	Ce ment	S and						
	58 3	1 422	40,5	5,5	182	F 300	W6	B35
	55 1	1 374	57,5	6,8	194	F 400	W1 6	B35

Conclusion

Based on the conducted research, it was established that fine-grained basalt fiber concrete possesses high physical, mechanical, and operational properties. The introduction of basalt fibers into the concrete strengthens the structure of the cement stone, reduces the formation of micro-cracks, and increases the strength of the concrete under compression and bending. At the same time, the uniform distribution of fibers along the matrix increases the density of the concrete and limits water penetration through capillary paths.

The test results demonstrated that the optimized composition of the basalt-fiber concrete possesses high waterproofing properties. The samples were tested without water filtration under a pressure of 1.6 MPa and were found to correspond to the W16 waterproofing grade. This makes it possible to effectively use this material in structures with high humidity and water pressure.

It was also found that the use of basalt fibers increases the frost resistance of concrete. The fibers reduce tensile stresses within the concrete and slow down the weathering processes resulting from freeze-thaw cycles. The resulting closed pores compensate for the expansion of the freezing water volume and maintain the integrity of the concrete structure.

Overall, basalt-fiber concrete is recommended as an effective and long-lasting composite material in modern construction due to its high strength, water resistance, wear resistance, and corrosion resistance.

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